

High-frequency neurostimulation of the right inferior parietal cortex alters the sense of agency: Results from tACS/tRNS and rTMS-EEG studies

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ABSTRACT

Background: Sense of agency (SoA) is the subjective experience of causing and controlling one's actions. Recent studies have linked SoA to gamma-band oscillations in the right inferior parietal lobule (IPL) and suggest that it can be modulated through external interventions using neurostimulation techniques.

Objective: This study aims to provide evidence for a causal role of the right IPL in SoA using multiple noninvasive brain stimulation methods (NIBS), electroencephalography (EEG), and a feedback manipulation task.

Methods: In two experiments, we investigated the effect of gamma band (60 Hz) transcranial alternating current stimulation (tACS), transcranial random noise stimulation (tRNS), low-frequency (1 Hz) repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation (rTMS), and high-frequency (10 Hz, 20 Hz) rTMS over the right IPL.

Results: As anticipated, gamma band tACS and high-frequency rTMS had distinct effects on SoA. Gamma band tACS enhanced the detection of non-self agency, while high-frequency rTMS impaired this capacity and reduced the overall SoA. EEG spectral analysis confirmed the impact of stimulation on the right IPL and highlighted the role of beta band oscillations.

Conclusion: Using the largest subject pool to date, our study provides causal evidence for the crucial role of the right IPL in processing SoA, particularly in detecting non-self agency arising from real-time sensorimotor mismatch comparison. Our findings suggest that external stimulation affects the comparator mechanism, rather than introducing prediction errors as previously proposed, and support the view that the right IPL is more closely associated with the implicit feeling of agency rather than with higher cognitive processes.

1. Introduction

The sense of agency (SoA) is the subjective experience of being the originator of an action: the one *causing something to move* (Gallagher, 2000), or *controlling the action* (Haggard and Tsakiris, 2009; Moore, 2016) and its consequences in the external world. This cognitive process plays a crucial role in how we engage with the outside world (Chambon et al., 2013). Impairments in SoA have been linked to various neuropsychiatric conditions such as schizophrenia (Kozáková et al., 2020; Farrer et al., 2004; Thakkar et al., 2017), obsessive-compulsive disorder (Tapal et al., 2017; Belayachi and Van der Linden, 2010), alien hand syndrome (Schaefer et al., 2010), and functional neurological disorders

(Edwards and Bhatia, 2012; Nahab et al., 2017).

Accumulating evidence suggests that the brain activity underlying the SoA can best be described as an interplay between the medio-frontal and parietal cortices (GA Zito et al., 2020; Sperduti et al., 2011; Brass and Haggard, 2008). The medial frontal areas, including the pre-supplementary motor area (pre-SMA) and supplementary motor area (SMA), are linked with the initiation of motor action (Fried et al., 2011; Haggard, 2008; Filevich et al., 2013; Guggisberg et al., 2011; Guggisberg and Mottaz, 2013) and the prediction of sensory consequences (Haggard and Whitford, 2004; Yomogida et al., 2010). Concurrently, the area broadly identified with inferior parietal lobule (IPL), temporo-parietal junction (TPJ) or posterior parietal cortex (PPC)

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plays a significant role in various processes associated with agency, as is the formation of intentions (Desmurget and Sirigu, 2009; Desmurget and Sirigu, 2012; Desmurget et al., 2009; Sirigu et al., 2004), processing of self/other information in motor tasks (GA Zito et al., 2020; Sperduti et al., 2011; Gallese et al., 2002; C Farrer et al., 2008; Chaminade and Decety, 2002; A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014; A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014; Aybek and Vuilleumier, 2016), the sense of self (for review see (Igelström and Graziano, 2017)), awareness of intention (Desmurget and Sirigu, 2012), action representation (Gallese et al., 2002; Bečev et al., 2021), and with comparison of motor plan with action outcomes (Gallese, 2005). SoA processing in this area has been particularly associated with gamma oscillations (Guggisberg et al., 2011; Guggisberg and Mottaz, 2013).

Here, we investigate the SoA at a rudimentary level, specifically as it relates to motor actions. At this level, the SoA can be understood through the *comparator model*, which was initially created to explain action monitoring and movement control (Wolpert et al., 1995) and subsequently broadened to encompass the processing of agency (Frith et al., 2000; Wen et al., 2015; Blakemore et al., 2002; Synofzik et al., 2008; Frith, 2005). The comparison of predicted consequences of an intended action with sensory feedback about the actual consequences of the action has been localized into the right-sided IPL/TPJ (C Farrer et al., 2008; A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014; Preston and Newport, 2008; Voon et al., 2010; Barr et al., 2011; David et al., 2008). Studies featuring incongruent visual feedback have shown that IPL/TPJ region plays a pivotal role in agency processing, (reviewed in Sperduti et al., 2011; Barr et al., 2011; David et al., 2008; Miele et al., 2011; Decety and Lamm, 2007; Crivelli and Balconi, 2017; Farrer et al., 2003), specifically in generating the non-agency experience (Chaminade and Decety, 2002; Moore et al., 2010; Nahab et al., 2011; Doricchi et al., 2022). Particularly, a gamma band activity in this region has been associated with sensory prediction error (van Pelt et al., 2016) and mismatch detection during motor actions (Zama et al., 2019), while concurrently a gamma coupling between IPL and pre-SMA characterizes a positive correspondence of the comparison (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014).

Neurostimulation studies revealed a complex relationship between the right IPL and the SoA. High-frequency (excitatory) 10 Hz rTMS increased reports of one's actions as externally manipulated (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014). However, this effect also occurred with a single pulse during a self/other task (Preston and Newport, 2008) and with a low-frequency (inhibitory) stimulation to the same area (GA Zito et al., 2020).

Despite a number of promising experimental studies suggesting a role for the right IPL in the SoA (Gallese, 2005), and heterogeneous findings regarding the effects of IPL neurostimulation on SoA (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014; Preston and Newport, 2008; GA Zito et al., 2020), cohesive experimental evidence for a causal role of this region—particularly in relation to the sensorimotor comparator—remains lacking.

This study aims to address this unresolved question. To this end, we employed multiple non-invasive brain stimulation (NIBS) techniques, with stimulation parameters specifically chosen to modulate gamma-band oscillations in the right IPL, as these oscillations have been associated with sensory prediction errors and mismatch detection. The effects of neurostimulation were assessed using a behavioral feedback manipulation task and electroencephalography (EEG).

2. Materials and methods

One of the most influential views understands SoA in terms of basic motor control principles and operationalizes it as an *ability* to distinguish between self-caused and externally caused effects (Grünbaum and Christensen, 2020; Charalampaki et al., 2022; Buchholz et al., 2019). This type of SoA studies often manipulates the predictability of action outcomes by introducing spatial deviation, drawing conceptually from the comparator model (Christensen and Grünbaum, 2018). The present

study builds upon this notion and quantifies SoA as the accuracy of self/other agency distinction. To investigate the causal role of IPL, we used two NIBS methods to externally manipulate the action-effect comparator. Experiment 1 employed tACS (transcranial alternate current stimulation) and tRNS (transcranial random noise stimulation) to facilitate the SoA by applying high-gamma (60 Hz) tACS and tRNS over left and right IPL. TACS has been successfully used to induce gamma oscillations in various brain regions (Santarnecchi et al., 2019; Dhaynaut et al., 2022; Helfrich et al., 2014; Sprugnoli et al., 2021; Voss et al., 2014; Naro et al., 2016; Benussi et al., 2022), but never in SoA studies. In Experiment 2 we employed rTMS (repeated transcranial magnetic stimulation) to compare the effects of excitatory and inhibitory rTMS over right IPL on behavioral performance in the SoA task, on band power and on parieto-frontal functional connectivity.

2.1. Experiment 1 (tACS, tRNS)

2.1.1. Participants

Eighteen healthy, right-handed participants (11 females, ages between 20 and 52, mean age = 30.8; SD = 8.6) with no reported neurological or psychiatric condition participated in this study. In accordance with the latest Declaration of Helsinki, all participants signed informed consent forms, and the study received approval from the Ethical Committee of National Institute of Mental Health, Czechia (case 118/19). Upon finishing all of the sessions, participants received a financial reward of CZK 2000 (~EUR 80) in cash. Due to the relative novelty of the tACS/tRNS neuromodulation method, clinical EEG and anatomical MRI scans were acquired and evaluated for all participants. From the initial pool of 24 volunteers, three were excluded due to incidental MRI findings, and the other three dropped out during the study. Details of inclusion and exclusion criteria in Appendix A.

2.1.2. Experimental design

The experiment was a double-blind, placebo-controlled, within-subject study with a 2×6 design with factors of *task* and *neuromodulation protocol*. Every subject participated in six experimental sessions (visits) with a minimum one-week wash-out period. Every session included both the control task and the sense of agency (SoA) tasks. To ensure an equal number of subjects in each sequence of neuromodulation conditions, participants were randomly assigned to one of two sequences of *task types* (SoA task first and control task second, or vice versa) and one of six sequences of six *neuromodulation protocols* (tACS 60 Hz left IPL, tACS 60 Hz right IPL, tRNS left IPL, tRNS right IPL, placebo and control site stimulation), following Williams' randomization design (Williams, 1949) with a block size of six.

2.1.3. Procedure

Each participant underwent an initial enrollment session, which included providing informed consent, a routine EEG assessed by a neurologist, acquisition of 3D coordinates of scalp electrodes for creating individual head model. Individual MR images acquired with a Siemens Magnetom Prisma 3T system (Siemens, Erlangen, Germany) were evaluated by radiologist and used to create a personalized head model for each participant.

The experimental part of the study consisted of six experimental sessions following the same script, starting with a shortened Profile of Mood States questionnaire (POMS) (Shacham, 1983; Stuchlíková et al., 2005). After that participants were fitted with an electrode net and underwent one of the neuromodulation protocols while performing a SoA task and control task (see Fig. 1 right). Each session concluded with a post-session POMS and Czech version of the Questionnaire of Sensations Related to Transcranial Electrical Stimulation (Antal et al., 2017; Klířová 2022).

2.1.4. Sense of agency task and control tasks

SoA task and control task are continuous-action dot-control tasks

Experiment 1

Fig. 1. Experimental protocol included intro session (left), calculation of individual settings conducted by researchers (center), and experimental sessions conducted in six visits (right).

that manipulate sensorimotor contingency through spatial noise, based on the joystick task of Kozáková (Kozáková et al., 2020), Virtual Pen task (Werner et al., 2014), Nielsen’s “Alien hand” line-tracing paradigm (Nielsen, 1963) and Jeannerod’s joystick task (C Farrer et al., 2008; Fournier et al., 1998). In both tasks, participants are facing a screen featuring multiple obstacles (see Fig. 2D). They use a computer mouse to control the cursor, keeping it moving in a steady motion over the screen and around obstacles for the entire block duration (~4 min). In the **SoA task**, participants were informed that researchers (i.e. other human agents) might intermittently interfere with the cursor’s movement, more or less noticeably, via an app on their mobile phones. They were asked to press a mouse button whenever they perceived the movement as being externally manipulated. To encourage accurate self/other discrimination reporting, accuracy scores were calculated at the end of each session, and participants received a reward of 1–3 Raffaello candies (Ferrero, Alba, Italy) based on their performance. Unknown to participants, cursor perturbations were controlled by the computer, alternating between sections with no deviation (0°) and sections introducing varying degrees of angular deviation: $\pm 10^\circ$, $\pm 20^\circ$,

$\pm 30^\circ$, and $\pm 40^\circ$

While the SoA task assessed both the sense of agency and sensorimotor processing, the control task focused solely on the sensorimotor action loop. The task closely resembled the SoA task but without any external interference in cursor movement. Instead, participants monitored for the appearance of a simple visual stimulus—a yellow circle around the cursor—and reported its onset. The timing of stimulus appearance and disappearance followed the same pattern as the cursor deviations in the SoA task. Details in Appendix A.

2.1.5. Neuromodulation

TACS and tRNS neuromodulation protocols with individualized settings were administered using a GTEN 100 device with 256-channel HCGSN net (Magstim EGL, Eugene, OR, USA). A personalized optimal current injection setting was determined for each participant following the procedure described in (Klířová et al., 2021). First, an individual head model was generated by segmenting white matter, gray matter, and background ratios using the Modal Image Pipeline (EGL, Eugene, OR, United States) based on anatomical MR images. This head model

Experiment 1

Fig. 2. Scheme of the procedure in Experiment 1. A: session structure in Experiment 1. B: the organization of individual task blocks with different obstacle layouts used. C: angular deviation applied throughout each of the blocks, with time on the horizontal axis and angular deviation on the vertical axis. D: Schematic of the SoA task used in the Experiment 1 and 2. In the task part, subjects moved a mouse cursor (a ball) freely around the obstacles while wearing a GTEN/EEG cap.

was then co-registered with the participant's GPS image to obtain an accurate conductivity model. Next, using GTEN Planning procedure (Luu et al., 2016), an optimized current injection electrode setting was calculated for each subject based on their individualized conductivity model (see Fig. 1 left and center). Details of neuromodulation protocols can be found in Appendix A.

2.2. Experiment 2 (rTMS-EEG)

2.2.1. Participants

Sixteen healthy volunteers (10 females, ages between 19 and 54, mean age = 31.3; SD = 10.13; all right-handed) entered the experiment after providing written consent. Inclusion and exclusion criteria and informed consent were handled identically as in Experiment 1. Part of the subject pool overlapped between Experiment 1 and Experiment 2.

2.2.2. Experimental design

The experiment was designed as a double-blind, placebo-controlled, within-subject study with a $2 \times 4 \times 4$ design with factors of *task type*, *external manipulation*, and *rTMS condition*. Every subject participated in four experimental sessions, following a wash-out period of one week or longer. Participants were randomly assigned to one of two different sequences of two task types (control task, SoA tasks - adapted from the Experiment 1 (see 2.1.4)), and one of four sequences of four rTMS conditions (20 Hz, 10 Hz, 1 Hz, and sham TMS), following William's

randomization design (Williams, 1949) with a block size of four. Throughout every session, the *external manipulation* factor was gradually varied across four angular levels (0° , $\pm 5^\circ$, $\pm 10^\circ$ and $\pm 20^\circ$). The change in degrees of deviation and dynamics of deviation onset were modified based on outcomes of Experiment 1 which suggested ceiling scale attenuation effect for interventions over 20° . Identically to the Experiment 1, each session was initiated and concluded with a post-session POMS (see Fig. 3).

2.2.3. rTMS administration

MagPro R30 equipment (Magventure®, Inc., Denmark) with a Cool d-B80 A/P double-cone coil was used to administer rTMS in a double-blinded study. The coil was placed horizontally in the anterior-posterior direction, tangential to the scalp. rTMS targeted the right inferior parietal lobe - corresponding to electrode 193 on the 256-channel HCGSN net. Four rTMS protocols were administered: 1 Hz rTMS, 10 Hz rTMS, 20 Hz rTMS, and sham rTMS. All active protocols were delivered at 100 % MT. Details in Appendix B.

2.2.4. EEG acquisition

EEG signal during tasks and resting state were recorded using a Magstim EGI GTEN 100 with a 256-channel HCGSN net using saline-solution electrodes (Magstim EGI, Eugene, OR, USA), scheme on Fig. B.2. Electrode impedances were maintained below 50 k Ω before starting the recording. Data were referenced to the vertex electrode and

Experiment 2

A

B

C

Fig. 3. Scheme of the procedure in Experiment 2. A: session structure in Experiment 2. B: the organization of individual task blocks with different obstacle layouts used. C: angular deviation applied throughout each of the blocks of the SoA task (left) and control task (right), with time on the horizontal axis and angular deviation on the vertical axis.

digitized at a 1000 Hz sampling rate. EEG and stimulation synchronization was achieved using an independent synchronization platform developed in-house at National Institute of Mental Health, Czech Republic. The platform is based on Raspberry Pi 4 and operates with temporal accuracy (time offset and jitter) below 1 ms.

Five EEG blocks were recorded during each session (see Fig. 3): a baseline resting-state block, two EEG blocks during task performance immediately following rTMS stimulation ($S + 5$ blocks) and two resting-state blocks after task completion ($S + 9$ blocks). The baseline and $S + 9$ blocks were acquired during resting-state EEG, with participants instructed to keep their eyes closed, refrain from focusing on anything specific, and avoid falling asleep during the 5-minute recording. The $S + 5$ blocks were recorded while participants performed the SoA task and the control task. The decision to examine EEG responses at two temporal intervals ($S + 5$ and $S + 9$) was motivated by the limited literature on the duration of high-frequency rTMS aftereffects on EEG, which range from approximately 5 to 20 min (Valero-Cabré et al., 2017; Thut and Pascual-Leone, 2010). While the $S + 9$ blocks reflect conventional resting-state recordings obtained after task completion, the $S + 5$ blocks were recorded during task performance, following only a ~ 5 min delay needed for EEG cap placement. These $S + 5$ recordings therefore offer critical insight into the earliest EEG aftereffects of the rTMS protocol.

2.3. Analysis

2.3.1. Experiment 1 and 2: Behavioral analysis

In both experiments, we investigated the influence of different neuromodulation / neurostimulation protocols on behavioral performance in the SoA task and control. SoA was operationalized as overall accuracy and monitored along with its two independent factors: non-self detection i.e. the capacity to register non-self actions as extraneous (specificity, true negative rate, TNR) and the self-action detection i.e. the capacity to recognize own actions as self-caused (sensitivity, true positive rate, TPR).

To evaluate differences in performance (SoA, TNR or TPR) from the placebo across the four stimulation conditions, we employed a linear mixed-effect model. The model controlled for individual performance in the control task and included random intercepts to account for between-subject variability in the repeated measures design (SoA \sim SoA-control + condition + (1|subjectId)). Statistical testing was performed using the Statterthwaite method, which has been shown to yield robust estimates (Luke, 2017). In the behavioral analysis, SoA was designated as the primary outcome, with TNR and TPR treated as secondary, nested analyses. Consequently, no correction for multiple comparisons was applied. The control-site condition was excluded from the analysis (see Appendix A). All statistical analyses were performed in R using RStudio (Team and others, 2013; Team, 2015), mixed-effect models were

performed using the package lme4 (Bates et al., 2015) and significance testing was conducted lmerTest package (Kuznetsova et al., 2017) which implements the Satterthwaite method.

2.3.2. Experiment 2: EEG analysis

2.3.2.1. EEG preprocessing: the effect of 20 Hz rTMS. EEG preprocessing for the $S + 5$ blocks was performed offline on data recorded during the SoA task. While the TD_BRAIN preprocessing pipeline (used for $S + 9$ blocks) is optimized for resting-state EEG, the $S + 5$ blocks were collected during task performance and were thus more prone to movement artifacts. Accordingly, manual preprocessing using BrainVision Analyzer 2.0 (Brainproducts, Gilching, Germany) was deemed more appropriate. The data were high-pass filtered (cutoff frequency: 1 Hz, 12 dB/octave, zero phase shift Butterworth filter) and low-pass filtered (48 Hz, 24 dB/octave). To minimize artifact contamination, 61 channels located closest to the neck were removed, and topographic interpolation was applied to any bad channels identified in the remaining subset of 195 channels. Ocular artifacts were detected and corrected using ocular ICA (VEOG channel: FP2, HEOG: F9) prior to re-referencing the data to the common average. Muscle and other residual artifacts were rejected using semi-automatic artifact detection based on a maximum amplitude difference of 120 μV over 200 ms and a voltage step threshold of 50 $\mu\text{V}/\text{ms}$. Thresholds were adjusted on per-dataset basis for cases with elevated high-frequency noise. Only subjects with at least 60 valid segments per condition were included in the analysis. For the $S + 5$ blocks, baseline could not be applied as it was recorded on resting subjects with eyes closed. Therefore, statistic was calculated on absolute band power values recorded during the SoA task. Power in the beta (13–30 Hz) and low-gamma (30–48 Hz) bands was calculated using the MNE Toolbox (Gramfort et al., 2013).

For the $S + 9$ blocks, EEG preprocessing and power spectral analysis were conducted offline using the Python-based TDBrain pipeline (Brainclinics Foundation, Nijmegen, the Netherlands) following the protocol from van Dijk et al. (2022) (van Dijk et al., 2022). Data from both the baseline resting-state and the post-SoA-task resting period were adapted for TDBrain in MNE toolbox (Gramfort et al., 2013) and filtered by Hamming-windowed FIR filter (0.5 Hz - 100 Hz passband). As in the $S + 5$ preprocessing, 61 neck electrodes were removed. The TDBrain preprocessing pipeline included artifact detection using the following thresholds: muscle artifacts (3 z-scores), extreme kurtosis ($\text{kurtosis} > 8$), extreme voltage swing ($> 200\mu\text{V}$), artifactual sharp baseline shifts (5 z-scores) and residuals of eye artifacts (correlation $r > 0.5$ with EOG channels). The EEG data were subsequently re-referenced to the average reference and segmented into 2000 ms epochs with 1000 ms overlap. Epochs containing artifacts were excluded from further analysis. Only subjects with a minimum 60 valid segments per condition were included. Absolute band power values from the post-task $S + 9$ blocks were baseline-corrected by subtracting the corresponding power from the baseline resting period. Methodological differences in the preprocessing of $S + 5$ and $S + 9$ blocks limit the possibility of directly comparing their statistical results.

2.3.2.2. EEG preprocessing: band power and connectivity analysis underlying SoA. This analysis was conducted on the same dataset used for the $S + 5$ blocks. Following the preprocessing steps described in 2.3.2.1, EEG data from the placebo condition were further segmented into *self* trials (0° angular deviation) and *non-self* trials ($\pm 10^\circ$ and $\pm 20^\circ$ deviations). Each 2000 ms epoch started 1000 ms after the onset of the block and was normalized to the total power within the 1–45 Hz frequency range. The segmented data were band-pass filtered using FIR filters for the alpha, theta and gamma frequency bands.

2.3.2.3. The effect of rTMS on beta and gamma band power. The band power analysis of block data compared the effects of rTMS stimulation

and placebo within a ROI surrounding the right IPL, comprising six channels (see Fig. B.2). The analysis was restricted to the 20 Hz rTMS condition, which had shown a significant effect on TNR. Continuous EEG signal from the right IPL was segmented into 1000 ms-long non-overlapping and artefact-free segments. The stimulation's after effect was assessed at two time points: during the task following the stimulation (onset at $S + 5$ min, eyes opened) and during the subsequent resting period (onset at $S + 9$ min, eyes closed).

A paired-samples Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons was used to assess statistical differences in both $S + 5$ and $S + 9$ blocks, due to the non-normal distribution of the data (as determined by the Shapiro-Wilk test). Effect sizes were calculated using the non-parametric r derived from the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The test was conducted as one-sided comparison, based on the a priori hypothesis that EEG power values would be lower in the placebo group.

2.3.2.4. Band power and functional connectivity. To investigate electrophysiological correlates of the SoA, we evaluated the band power during self trials and non-self trials in the alpha, gamma and theta bands in the right IPL and pre-SMA. Alpha band power in central and parietal regions has been previously linked to both higher SoA (Bu-Omer et al., 2021; Kang et al., 2015; Verbaarschot et al., 2015) and reduced SoA (Zito et al., 2023). Gamma band power has also been associated with SoA (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014), while theta and alpha activity has been found to negatively correlate with agency (Bu-Omer et al., 2021; Zito et al., 2023). Moreover, we performed an exploratory analysis of functional connectivity between right IPL and pre-SMA as a function of SoA. Gamma band coupling between these regions was expected to be stronger during self-agency events as observed in high-gamma band (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014).

First, the amplitude envelope in each band was extracted using the Hilbert transform for subsequent band power and connectivity analysis. Second, for both the band power and functional connectivity analyses, the response was assessed in cluster of seven scalp channels representing the right IPL and pre-SMA (see Fig. B.2). The analysis of potential band power changes related to self-agency was conducted on averaged power envelopes using paired T-test, as normality was not rejected by the Shapiro-Wilk tests. Bidirectional connectivity between IPL and pre-SMA was assessed in gamma band (30–48 Hz), using the power envelope correlation method. Correlations were calculated across all channel pairs between the right IPL and pre-SMA clusters, and the resulting values were averaged to estimate connectivity between these regions. Effect size was computed from the one-sided paired t -test using Cohen's d . A one-sided test was employed based on the a priori hypothesis that EEG power values would be lower in the self group. Only non-overlapping, artefact-free segments were included in the statistical analysis.

2.3.2.5. Statistical analysis. Power in bands was calculated using the Python's MNE Toolbox (Gramfort et al., 2013), the connectivity estimation was done using the Python MNE-connectivity library (Li et al., 2024). Statistics for both $S + 5$ and $S + 9$ blocks were calculated in R, using RStudio (Team and others, 2013; Team, 2015).

3. Results

3.1. Experiment 1 (tACS, tRNS): Behavioral results

3.1.1. Sense of agency

The mixed-effects model reveals no significant differences between conditions compared to placebo. We hypothesized that 60 Hz tACS will impair SoA by introducing non-self bias, while the tRNS will improve SoA due to the effect of stochastic resonance (Potok et al., 2021). However, the results did not show any significant effect of these

interventions on SoA for either hemisphere (Fig. 4, left). Data collected through the POMS questionnaires were intended to assess the potential effect of neuromodulation on affective state and were not analyzed in the present study.

3.1.2. Gamma band tACS of the right IPL improves the detection of non-self agency

The mixed-effect model indicated a significantly higher non-self agency detection (TNR) score following tACS over the right IPL compared to placebo ($\beta = 0.038$, $SE = 0.017$, $p = 0.032$). There was also a significant effect of sensorimotor performance, with a higher control task score associated with a higher SoA score ($\beta = 1.333$, $SE = 0.567$, $p = 0.020$). When considering only angular manipulations unaffected by floor and ceiling effects (i.e. $\pm 10^\circ$ deviations), the effect of tACS over the right IPL on non-self agency detection improvement was even greater ($\beta = 0.045$, $SE = 0.019$, $p = 0.017$), with the borderline insignificant effect of sensorimotor performance ($\beta = 0.598$, $SE = 0.327$, $p = 0.069$).

Regarding self-agency (TPR), there were no significant effects of any of the tACS/tRNS protocols compared to placebo, and no effect of sensorimotor performance on the SoA task (Fig. 4). However, the outcome was greatly influenced by the ceiling effect – most subjects found correctly detecting their own agency relatively easy.

3.2. Experiment 2 (rTMS-EEG): Behavioral results

3.2.1. High-frequency rTMS disrupts SoA

The mixed-effect model showed significantly reduced SoA following 10 Hz rTMS ($\beta = -0.023$, $SE = 0.01$, $p = 0.024$) and 20 Hz rTMS ($\beta = -0.038$, $SE = 0.01$, $p < 0.001$) compared to placebo, see in Fig. 5. There was also a significant effect of sensorimotor performance ($\beta = 1.314$, $SE = 0.56$, $p = 0.022$). Weak and medium angular deviations ($\pm 5^\circ$ and $\pm 10^\circ$) were too difficult for subjects to detect (Fig. D.2).

3.2.2. High-frequency rTMS disrupts the detection of non-self agency

High-frequency (20 Hz) rTMS significantly reduced non-self agency detection ($\beta = -0.048$, $SE = 0.02$, $p = 0.023$) while none of the active rTMS protocols had any significant effect on self-agency detection (TPR), see in Fig. 5.

3.3. Experiment 2 (rTMS-EEG): EEG results

3.3.1. The effect of 20 Hz rTMS on beta and gamma band power

At the $S + 5$ timepoint, 20 Hz rTMS was correlated with significantly higher power in the beta band ($Z = -1.98$, $p = 0.049$ after correction, $r = 0.528$) and borderline insignificant changes in gamma band power ($Z = -1.91$, $p = 0.058$ after correction, $r = 0.512$) in the right IPL (Fig. 6). Two subjects out of 16 were excluded as outliers in this analysis. At the $S + 9$ time point, no significant effect of 20 Hz rTMS on brain activity was found.

3.3.2. Band power and functional connectivity underlying SoA

Out of the total 16 subjects, one was excluded due to missing markers. Additionally, one subject was excluded as an outlier in the analysis of alpha and gamma bands, and two subjects were excluded in the analysis of the theta band.

The paired samples Wilcoxon test showed no significant difference in alpha band power and gamma band power between self-blocks and non-self blocks in the right IPL. For theta band power in the right IPL, there was a significant rise in relative power $T = -2.01$, $p = 0.034$, significant when uncorrected, with Cohen's $d = -0.56$, see in Fig. 7. In pre-SMA, none of the three bands showed significant changes between self and non-self conditions (see Fig. D.3). No changes in right IPL to pre-SMA connectivity in the gamma band were observed between the self-agency and non-self agency conditions.

4. Discussion

Our findings provide causal evidence supporting the hypothesis that the right IPL is a key region involved in processing the sense of agency and multisensory inconsistency. As anticipated, gamma band tACS and high-frequency rTMS influenced SoA differently. Importantly, the effects of both NIBS interventions on SoA were selective, indicating that changes in performance were not due to general sensorimotor processes. EEG spectral analysis confirmed that the mechanism manipulated by rTMS is localized within the right IPL. To our knowledge, this study is the first to explore electrophysiological changes underlying SoA disrupted by noninvasive brain stimulation. Besides the conventionally reported non-self agency detection (TNR, specificity), it evaluates also self-agency detection (TPR, sensitivity) and SoA operationalized as overall accuracy.

Fig. 4. Experiment 1: Sense of Agency (overall accuracy), self-agency (TPR), and non-self agency (TNR) in the SoA tasks compared across the five neuromodulation conditions. Ceiling effect in TPR is visible in both the tasks, suggesting that even the SoA task is mostly easy for the subjects. Compared to the placebo, 60 Hz tACS of the right IPL significantly facilitated the detection of non-self agency.

Fig. 5. Experiment 2: Sense of Agency (overall accuracy), self-agency (TPR) and non-self agency (TNR) in the SoA tasks compared across the four rTMS conditions. The ceiling effect in TPR suggests that detection of own agency is easy for most of the subjects. Compared to the placebo, 20 Hz rTMS showed a consistent effect reducing sense of agency while also reducing the detection of non-self agency. Additionally, the detection of non-self agency was also significantly reduced by 10 Hz rTMS.

Fig. 6. Experiment 2: beta and gamma power in the right IPL at two time points ($S + 5$, $S + 9$) following rTMS. For the $S + 5$ time point, statistics were calculated on absolute band power values recorded during the SoA task. For the $S + 9$ time point, absolute band power from post-SoA-task resting period was individually controlled by subtracting corresponding band power from baseline resting.

4.1. Different NIBS techniques differentially affect the SoA

The first key finding is that 60 Hz tACS facilitates the detection of non-self agency. The Experiment 1 revealed that 60 Hz gamma band tACS and over the right IPL improves non-self agency, i.e. ability to recognize external intrusions. This is in line with our hypothesis that 60 Hz tACS would induce non-self bias by promoting gamma oscillations in the IPL.

The second key discovery is that high-frequency rTMS disrupts recognition of non-self agency. Our results show that high-frequency (20 Hz and 10 Hz) rTMS of the right IPL impairs the SoA, which is mediated by reduction of the ability to detect a lack of control during external intrusions (TNR). EEG analysis confirmed that the 20 Hz rTMS causally affected electrophysiological activity in the stimulated area, with effects lasting approximately 5 min, but not 9 min. Low-frequency (1 Hz) rTMS which is inhibitory, yielded no effect on SoA. Contrary to expectations, the observed synchronization was limited to the beta band with no impact on low-gamma, suggesting that the rTMS impact on SoA is mediated by beta activity. Beta band EEG activity has been associated

with SoA in various contexts and likely reflects more complex processes related to mismatch detection and error signaling (Bu-Omer et al., 2021; Zito et al., 2023) but also high-level factors like belief in agency (Buchholz et al., 2019). The absence of gamma band effect is potentially due to short carryover duration in higher bands (Valero-Cabré et al., 2017; Thut and Pascual-Leone, 2010).

4.2. Parietal comparator and agency

Our findings reinforce the role of the right IPL in SoA, though we identified different underlying factors. Contrary to some previous studies, we did not observe a reduced capacity to detect self-agency following high-frequency rTMS (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014) (see Fig. 8) or single-pulse TMS (Preston and Newport, 2008). Instead, our results show that high-frequency rTMS (10 Hz and 20 Hz) significantly reduced non-self detection (TNR), consistent with findings using anodal (excitatory) tDCS (Hughes, 2018) and inhibitory theta-burst TMS (GA Zito et al., 2020) in the same area.

Ritterband-Rosenbaum, Karabanov, et al., (2014) proposed that

Fig. 7. Experiment 2: Boxplot of power in alpha, gamma, and theta bands. Self-agency is associated with higher activity in the theta band compared to the manipulated condition, however, it does not survive Bonferroni correction.

Fig. 8. Schematic illustration of the NIBS effect on SoA, specifically on the detection of self-agency (TPR) and non-self agency (TNR). Generally, a greater action-effect discrepancy induced by external manipulation is easier to detect, resulting in higher accuracy (SoA) and higher detection rates (TPR, TNR). However, very small and very large discrepancies are affected by floor and ceiling effects. The 20 Hz rTMS decreases SoA, as measured by accuracy, and similarly reduces non-self agency. In contrast, 60 Hz tACS improves specificity, though the effect is not strong enough to significantly enhance overall SoA. Not proportional.

rTMS over right IPL adds noise which raises a prediction error in the action-effect comparison, affecting conditions with high feeling of agency like self-controlled trials or trials with very small action-effect discrepancy (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014). Our results challenge this, suggesting that rTMS disrupts mismatch detection in the comparator, impacting the detection of non-self agency in trials with strong deviations more than small deviations. Detection of correspondence (i.e. self-agency) seems to be processed independently from non-self agency (Charalampaki et al., 2022), remaining unaffected by rTMS.

This discrepancy in results may be due to the different effects of asynchronous (offline) rTMS used in our study compared to online rTMS used in Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al. (2014) (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014) and in Preston study (Preston and Newport, 2008), or due to different response heuristics employed by the subjects. During challenging tasks, subjects might develop strategies (response biases) based on contextual cues about self/non-self trial ratios which differed between the studies. While these accidental biases are unable to improve

an individual's overall accuracy (SoA), they can systematically impact a responder's sensitivity (self-agency detection rate) and specificity (non-self agency detection rate), complicating comparisons between earlier studies that do not report overall accuracy. The unusual construction of rTMS conditions (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014), comparing IPL stimulation against vertex stimulation which likely affects SMA and pre-SMA linked to motor predictions (Shimizu et al., 2020; Hsu et al., 2011) and a non-standard placebo, further complicates comparisons.

Additionally, this study provides new insights into the electrophysiological markers of SoA. Our results did not show any link between changes in self/non-self agency detection and parietal low-gamma power. Furthermore, there was no difference in parietal low-gamma band power or in low-gamma band connectivity between right IPL and pre-SMA across self-agency and non-self agency conditions. These findings suggest that the proposed roles of parietal gamma oscillations in sensorimotor comparison and gamma band connectivity between the right IPL and pre-SMA in the SoA might be limited to high-gamma band,

where some positive effects have been reported (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014). This is complemented by our observation of theta band synchronization in right IPL during non-self agency intrusions (significant when uncorrected) which potentially reflects the suppression of conflicting information during sensorimotor comparison (Kang et al., 2015). This finding aligns with studies suggesting anti-correlation of central theta and SoA (Zito et al., 2023; Jeunet et al., 2018). However, contrary to expectation, no corresponding changes were observed in the pre-SMA.

The right IPL has been implicated in both low-level factors of the SoA such as sensorimotor comparison and prediction error (Zama et al., 2019), as well as in higher-level attributions of agency (Buchholz et al., 2019; Ohata et al., 2021). Our study contributes to this ongoing discussion by providing further insights into the function of the parietal sensorimotor comparator. Sensorimotor comparison, a low-level, automatic action monitoring process involves detecting discrepancies between visual, proprioceptive, and motor inputs and the expected movement consequences. This comparison is a key factor in the formation of the feeling of agency, the bottom-up component of SoA (M Synofzik et al., 2008; Synofzik et al., 2009; Synofzik et al., 2013; David et al., 2011). Our findings align with the multifactorial model of agency (M Synofzik et al., 2008; Vosgerau and Synofzik, 2012), which posits that the right IPL is responsible for the complex comparison of re-afferent sensory inputs with predictions made from efferent copies.

The right IPL likely does not directly engage in the higher cognitive processes that underlie conscious reflection on whether or not an action was caused by someone else (i.e. judgment of agency) (Miele et al., 2011; Karabanov et al., 2017), instead, it plays a broader role in monitoring the consistency of various action-related signals and integrating them (Valérian et al., 2014), which is a key cue for (pre-reflective) feeling of agency (David et al., 2008; Synofzik et al., 2013; David et al., 2011). Our observation is consistent with the idea that premotor areas including pre-SMA are involved in movement preparation (Soon et al., 2008) and the prediction of movement consequences (Moore et al., 2010), with these predictions being transmitted to the right IPL/TPJ for a comparison with sensory feedback (GA Zito et al., 2020; C Farrer et al., 2008; Jeannerod et al., 2003; Thézé et al., 2020). This mismatch detection is primarily carried out by the right supra-marginal gyrus, right temporo-parietal junction (Miele et al., 2011; Nahab et al., 2011), and angular gyrus (Farrer et al., 2003). Contrastingly, detection of correspondence is associated with left IPL (Doricchi et al., 2022) and pre-SMA (Miele et al., 2011).

4.3. Conclusion

Taken together this study is the first to apply tACS and rTMS with offline EEG to investigate the causal mechanisms of agency. Using the largest subject pool to date, we demonstrated that the right inferior parietal lobule plays a crucial role in the sense of agency, particularly in detecting negative agency (non-self agency). Gamma band (60 Hz) tACS improved the detection rate of non-self agency, while high-frequency (20 Hz) rTMS disrupted this capacity. EEG analysis highlighted the beta band's key role in agency processing.

Our findings suggest that the IPL is essential for real-time action-effect comparison, associated with the implicit feeling of agency (David et al., 2008; Zama et al., 2019), rather than being directly involved in higher cognitive processes of agency and self-attribution. It appears that external stimulation affects the comparator mechanism rather than introducing an error per se, as previously assumed (A Ritterband-Rosenbaum et al., 2014).

Future research on the neuromodulation of SoA could focus on enhancing other-agency detection through gamma band (tACS) and parietal gamma neurofeedback (see (Zito et al., 2023)) combined with simultaneous EEG recording. Further studies should also explore the role of beta oscillations in action-effect comparison in the right IPL and the communication of prediction errors from the right IPL to the pre-SMA.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used OpenAI's ChatGPT tool in order to check grammar, improve language and readability of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

O. Bečev: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **O. Laskov:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **E. Bakštejn:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Formal analysis. **J. Štrobl:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Formal analysis. **J. Hubený:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Resources, Formal analysis. **N. Biacková:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **N. Schlezingerová:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **T. Novák:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **P. Mohr:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **M. Klírová:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Tomas Novak reports a relationship with BTL zdravotnická technika, a.s. that includes: funding grants. Monika Klírová reports a relationship with BTL zdravotnická technika, a.s. that includes: consulting or advisory and funding grants. Tomas Novak reports a relationship with DEYMED Diagnostic s.r.o. that includes: travel reimbursement. Monika Klírová reports a relationship with DEYMED Diagnostic s.r.o. that includes: consulting or advisory and travel reimbursement. Monika Klírová reports a relationship with BrainsWay Ltd that includes: travel reimbursement. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability statement

Data available on request due to privacy/ethical restrictions

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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